

CONCLUSION.

The parachors observed and calculated are in good agreement. This leads to the conclusion that the quadrivalent tellurium compounds possess a structure, in which the central tellurium atom is surrounded by a shell of ten electrons; four pairs of which are shared constituting four normal linkages and the fifth is a 'lone' pair. This view of expansion of the valency group beyond the normal octet in the quadrivalent tellurium compounds is further supported by the work of Simons (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 3488) in the case of tellurium tetrachloride.

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Analytical Uses of Nessler's Reagent. Detection of Aldehydes. Quantitative Estimation of Glucose. Part I.

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Methods which are ordinarily used for the estimation of glucose are often found to be attended with experimental difficulties. In case of Fehling's or Pavy's method the process is not only indirect, *i.e.*, a standard solution of pure glucose is required for comparison, but invariably gives discordant results on account of the easy oxidisability of cuprous oxide which is formed. The present work was undertaken in order to simplify the process of estimation and to eliminate other attendant difficulties. Our attention was drawn to two papers by Gros and Bougault (*J. Pharm. chim.*, 1922, **26**, 5, 170), in which they made a statement that Nessler's reagent could be suitably used for the estimation of some ketones and aldehydes, as an example of which they gave details of the estimation of acetone in urine. It was thought worth investigating whether a similar process should be applicable to the estimation of glucose. According to Gros and Bougault ketones are treated with Nessler's reagent and the mixture, thus obtained, is neutralised and treated with excess of standard iodine solution when the mercury which is formed goes into solution; the excess of iodine is then titrated back. This method

was tested with a standard solution of carefully dried purest glucose (Bacto dextrose-difco standard) and after numerous experiments conditions have been so standardised that it gives quantitative results (cf. Tables III and IV) using various concentrations. Comparative experiments were done with Fehling's solution (Table V) and with pathological urine (Table VI).

In order to see whether the limited observations of Gros and Bougault could be extended to all aldehydes and ketones, we repeated at first their experiments under the conditions described by them but surprisingly we have not been able to substantiate their results. For example the above authors stated that acetone, methyl-ethyl ketone, *cyclohexanone* trimethyl*cyclohexanone*, acetophenone, *p*-methoxyacetophenone reduced alkaline Nessler's reagent, whereas we found negative results in all cases.

It has been further found after experiments with numerous aldehydes and ketones that in general, ketones do not reduce alkaline Nessler's solution but aldehydes do (cf. Table I). In view of striking discrepancy of our results from those of Gros and Bougault we repeated our results several times with carefully purified substances but we could not corroborate them in any case. In the course of the experiments several exceptions (which can be otherwise explained) have been found (cf. Table II).

(1) Hydroxyaldehydes do not reduce but when the OH-group is protected usual reduction occurs.

(2) Hydroxyketones like benzoin and fructose reduce.

It has been found that K_2HgI_4 in strongly alkaline medium is easily and rapidly reduced. The strength of alkali is an important factor in the case of the reduction of the reagent with glucose or fructose. The extent of reduction depends on the strength and nature of the alkali (NaOH, KOH or Na_2CO_3) and temperature of the reaction. Thus it has been found that if 10% NaOH solution be used and the reactants are heated, the oxidation of glucose and fructose proceeds to an extent equivalent to the absorption of 5 atoms of oxygen per molecule of the sugar taken. On the contrary, if 10% Na_2CO_3 solution be used, the oxidation of glucose corresponds to the absorption of 2 atoms of oxygen, but that of fructose proceeds still further.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The Nessler's reagent used had the composition: $HgCl_2$ (2.5 g.), KI (8 g.), water (100 c.c.), NaOH (50 c.c., 30%). A few drops of

the substance to be tested were taken in a test tube and 1 c.c. of the reagent was added and gently heated if necessary. The following table gives the results with aldehydes and ketones.

TABLE I.

Substance.	Observation.	Temp.	Substance.	Observation.	Temp.
Formaldehyde	Reduction is rapid from red, yellow and then into black.	Takes place in the cold.	Furfuraldehyde	Red to black	Cold.
Acetaldehyde	"	"	Cinnamic aldehyde	Yellow to black	"
Propyl aldehyde	Rapid reduction into Hg.	"	Benzaldehyde	Red to black.	"
Aldehyde-C ₈	Reduction into black Hg.	Facilitated if gently heated.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	"	"
Aldehyde-C ₉	"	"	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	"	"
Aldehyde-C ₁₀	"	"	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	"	"
Aldehyde-C ₁₁	"	"	Paraldehyde	"	"
Aldehyde-C ₁₂	"	"	Acetone	No reduction.	Hot or cold.
Glyoxal	Reduction from red to black.	In the cold.	Methylethyl ketone	"	"
Chloral hydrate	"	"	Acetophenone	"	"
Heliotropin	Yellow, red, black.	"	Benzophenone	"	"
			<i>cyclo</i> Hexanone	"	"

The following table gives the results of exceptional cases with aldehydes and ketones.

TABLE II.

Substance.	Observation.	Temp.
Salicylaldehyde	Does not reduce.	Neither in the hot nor in the cold.
Vanillin	"	"
Anisaldehyde	Red to black.	In the cold.
Veratric aldehyde	"	"
Fructose	"	"
Benzoin	"	"

Estimation of glucose.—Glucose solution (standard 10 c.c.) was mixed with K₂HgI₄ solution (35 c.c.) contained in a litre flask and then 50 c.c. of Na₂CO₃ solution (10%) were added. The mixture was slowly heated, when the reduction soon commenced. The heating was continued to boiling until the whole liquid became clear and a black precipitate was found to settle at the bottom of the flask. The flask was then removed, the solution cooled and acidified with glacial acetic acid

(15 c.c.). Then 25 c.c. of *N*/10-iodine solution were added and the contents of the flask were thoroughly shaken until the finely divided black precipitate completely dissolved. The excess of iodine was then titrated by *N*/10-thiosulphate. The actual titration figures are given below

TABLE III.

1.6356 G. of glucose dissolved in 250 c.c. of water and 10 c.c. taken in each case.

0.803 <i>N</i> /10-iodine solution added.	0.918 <i>N</i> /10-hypo required.	Found.	Glucose taken.	Error.
25 c.c.	5.95 c.c.	1.6356	1.6278	0.48%
25	5.9	1.6356	1.6337	0.1
25	5.9	1.6356	1.6337	0.1
25	6.0	1.6356	1.6220	0.8

The method is being extended to the estimation of sucrose and other disaccharides.

TABLE IV.

(K_2HgI_4 method).

Strength per litre.	Comp.	Volume taken.	I_2 -soln. added.	<i>N</i> /10-Hypo required.		Glucose in the solution. (A - B) × 0.0045.	Actual wt. of glucose present in the soln.
				Before oxidation (A).	After oxidation (B).		
21.4336 g.	2.1433%	5 c.c.	50 c.c.	47.4 c.c.	23.6 c.c.	0.1071 g.	0.10716 g.
0.8572	0.0857	25	25	23.7	18.98	0.02146	0.02143
1.7144	0.1714	25	25	23.7	14.2	0.04275	0.04286
2.5720	0.2572	10	25	23.7	18.0	0.02565	0.02572
0.4286	0.0428	25	25	23.7	21.31	0.01075	0.01071
0.2143	0.0214	25	25	23.7	22.51	0.005355	0.005358

TABLE V.

(Fehling's solution with methylene blue as internal indicator).

1 c c. Fehling's soln. = 0.001543 g. of glucose.

Strength per litre.	Comp.	Fehling's soln.	Sugar soln. required.	Sugar calc.	Sugar present (Actual amount).
21.4336 g.	2.1433%	75 c.c.	5.4 c.c.	0.1157 g.	0.11574 g.
			5.4	0.1157	
0.8572	0.0857	25	45.8	0.03920	0.03858
			45.5	0.03880	
			46	0.03940	
1.7144	0.1714	25	23	0.03943	0.03858
			23.5	0.04000	
			23	0.03943	
0.4286	0.0428	10	38	0.01628	0.01543
			37	0.01586	
			37	0.01586	
0.2143	0.0214	5	40	0.008573	0.007715
			40	0.008573	
			39	0.008359	

TABLE VI.

Analysis of sugar in normal urine with glucose by K_2HgI_4 method.

100 C.c. urine contains 0.7980 g. of glucose.

0.7587 N/10-Hypo
required.

Volume of urine solution taken.	Iodine solution added.	Before oxidation (A).	After oxidation (B).	Glucose in the urine soln. (A - B) × 0.7587 × 0.0045.	Actual glucose in urine soln.
5 c.c.	25 c.c.	31.25 c.c.	19.6 c.c.	0.0398	
5	25	31.25	19.6	0.0398	0.0399
5	25	31.25	19.65	0.0396	